

STGT Multiple Access Beamforming System Modelling and Analysis

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Abstract

This paper provides a detailed modelling on the key elements of the Tracking and Data Relay Satellite Systems (TDRSS) S-Band Multiple Access (MA) return service and presents the beamforming and nulling operations in Second TDRSS Ground Terminal (STGT). The performance of beamforming, nulling and calibration processes is also analyzed.

1. Introduction

TDRSS MA return link service uses Code Division Multiple Access (CDMA) and Spatial Division Multiple Access (SDMA) for all users to share the same frequency channel. The CDMA operation is characterized by 3.06 Mcps user PN code while the SDMA is accomplished by using a phased-array antenna at TDRS with its beamforming performed at the STGT. This paper provides a detailed modelling on the key elements of the MA Return (MAR) link service and discusses the beamforming and nulling operations at the STGT. The performance of beamforming, nulling and calibration processes is also analyzed.

In Section 2, the operation of the MA system in support of the MAR service is first described. The beamforming and nulling processes are analyzed in Section 3. In Section 4, the calibration process is described with its performance evaluated.

2. System Modelling

A simplified diagram of the MAR system architecture is shown in Figure 1 [1]. The operation of the MA system in support of the MAR service is as follows. Up to 10 MAR users can transmit their data to TDRS using Pseudo-random-noise (PN) spread S-band signals. A calibration beacon is also transmitted from STGT to TDRS for the purpose of performing the phase calibration. The TDRS receives these MAR signals via its body-mounted 30-element antenna array. The received signals at each antenna element are upconverted into Frequency Division Multiplexed (FDM) Ku-band channels spaced 7.5 MHz apart. These FDM MAR signals together with the telemetry signal are amplified by the TWT and transmitted to the STGT. At STGT the FDM MAR signal is demultiplexed and downconverted into 30 channels, called element channels, centered at 29.75 MHz, in the Element Separator. These element channel signals feed twelve independent beamformers with one for the beacon, ten for MA users and one for spare. Each beamformer can be divided into two major parts. The first part consists of an Analog to Digital converter, a Variable Tap Delay Line and a Quadrature Splitter (AD_VTDL_QS). The second part is an Advanced Ground Implemented Phase Array (AGIPA). The AD_VTDL_QS first converts the analog signal to allow digital implementation in the beamformer. It then extracts the real and imaginary part of a PN spread QPSK signal in the element

channel with appropriate delay adjustment. The AGIPA determines an optimal weight based on certain optimization criterion. This weight is then used to adjust the amplitude and phase of each element channel signal and sums the resulting modified signals. This operation electrically points the 30-element satellite array in the direction of the desired MAR user.

A PN spread QPSK signal generated from user u can be represented by

$$S'_u(t) = a_u P_{u,I}(t) d_{u,I}(t) \cos(\omega t + \theta_u) - b_u P_{u,Q}(t) d_{u,Q}(t) \sin(\omega t + \theta_u) \\ = A'_u \cos[\omega t + \phi_u(t) + \theta_u] \quad u = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 10 \quad (1)$$

where $u=1, 2, \dots, 10$ stand for 10 possible MA users, while $u=0$ is used to denote the beacon signal transmitted from STGT. $P_{u,I}(t)$, $P_{u,Q}(t)$, $d_{u,I}(t)$, and $d_{u,Q}(t)$ stand for PN and data sequences for I, Q channels for user u . The values of $P_{u,I}(t)$, $P_{u,Q}(t)$, $d_{u,I}(t)$, and $d_{u,Q}(t)$ are assumed to be 1 or -1. The beacon signal contains PN sequence only, therefore $d_{0,I}(t) = d_{0,Q}(t) = 1$ and can be neglected. The I, Q power ratio is adjusted by selecting proper values of a_u and b_u . The amplitude, A'_u , and the phase, $\phi_u(t)$, of the PN spread QPSK signal for user u is given by

$$A'_u = \sqrt{a_u^2 + b_u^2} \\ \phi_u(t) = \tan^{-1} \frac{b_u P_{u,Q}(t) d_{u,Q}(t)}{a_u P_{u,I}(t) d_{u,I}(t)} \quad u = 1, 2, \dots, 10$$

and

$$(2)$$

$$\phi_0(t) = \tan^{-1} \frac{b_0 P_{0,Q}(t)}{a_0 P_{0,I}(t)}$$

A far-field user signal arriving at the antenna array would be different at the thirty elements only by a time delay dependent on the coordinates of the array elements and the look angle of the user. The users look angle for user u is defined by Φ_u and Θ_u as illustrated in Figure 2. Let the direction cosine of the user be $(\alpha_u, \beta_u, \gamma_u)$ and let the coordinate of the k -th array element be (x_k, y_k, z_k) as shown in Figure 2. The path delay of the u -th user signal received by the k -th element, relative to the element located at $(0,0,0)$, is

$$\delta_{u,k} = \{\alpha_u \cdot x_k + \beta_u \cdot y_k + \gamma_u \cdot z_k\} / c \quad (3)$$

where c is the speed of the light. The MAR signal received by the k -th array element can be specified by

$$E_k(t) = \sum_{u=0}^{10} \sqrt{G_u} A'_u \cos[\omega(t - \delta_{u,k}) + \phi_u(t - \delta_{u,k}) + \theta_u] + n''_k(t) \quad (4)$$

where G_u stands for the gain of the array elements for user u . Dependent on the Φ_u angle, the element gain pattern is given by

$$G_u = 39.81 \cdot \{\sin^2(5.614 \Phi_u) / (5.614 \Phi_u)^2\} \quad \Phi_u \text{ in radian} \quad (5)$$

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The element gain is $G_U = 39.81$ (= 16 dB) for a user at nadir direction, and it is 13.3 dB for a user at the edge of the ± 13.5 degree coverage zone. Although the element gain pattern may vary slightly among the array elements, it is assumed each array element has the same pattern to simplify the analysis. Thus the element gain depends on the MA user only and can be combined together with A'_U . Also in Eq.(4), we neglect the propagation delay between the MA users since at STGT there is a dedicated AGIPA for each user. What is important for each user is the differential delay between array elements, $\delta_{U,k}$, $k=1,2,\dots,30$. The maximum differential delay is determined by the maximum distance between elements and the maximum user look angle Φ_{max} . The MAR has the coverage of 27 degree field of view, i.e. $\Phi_{max}=13.5$. The maximum distance between elements is 119.4 cm. The maximum differential delay is then calculated to be 1.86 ns. This delay is insignificant compared with PN chip duration. On the other hand, since the carrier frequency is 2287.5 MHz, the maximum phase difference, $\omega \cdot \delta_{U,k}$, can be 26.733 in radian. Therefore, the relative carrier phase shift of the signals received by the array elements can be any value in $[0, 2\pi]$. Denote this phase shift as $\phi_{U,k}$, i.e.

$$\phi_{U,k} = -\omega \cdot \delta_{U,k} = -2\pi \cdot 2287.5 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \delta_{U,k} \quad (6)$$

and let $A_u = \sqrt{G_u} A'_u$. Eq. (4) can be rewritten as

$$E_k(t) = \sum_{u=0}^{10} A_u \cos [\omega t + \phi(t-\delta_{U,k}) + \theta_u + \phi_{U,k}] + n''_k(t) \quad (7)$$

$k = 1, 2, \dots, 30$

where $n''_k(t)$ stands for the total noise received in the k-th array element including the background radiance noise and internal thermal noise, i.e.

$$n''_k(t) = n_b(t) + n_{T_k}(t) \quad (8)$$

where $n_b(t)$ is the background radiance noise observed at the array antenna with noise temperature of 50°K. However, after beamforming this noise temperature may increase more than two hundred degree Kelvin. $n_{T_k}(t)$ stands for the internal thermal noise generated inside the TDRS with 390°K noise temperature. The background radiance noise is assumed to be coherent to all the array elements while the internal thermal noise is independent among the array elements. Both noise are assumed to be Gaussian processes.

The received element channel signals are then going through the processes of FDM, downlink propagation, and De-FDM. This signal handling introduces extraneous but fixed, time dependent, and frequency dependent distortions on amplitude, phase, and time delay in the element channels. At the output of the Element Separator, the k-th element channel signal can be modelled by

$$E'_k(t) = \sum_{u=0}^{10} \sqrt{G_k} \cdot A_u \cos [\omega_{IF} t + \phi_u(t-\delta_{U,k}-\delta_k) + \theta_u + \phi_{U,k} + \psi_k] + \sqrt{G_k} \cdot n'_k(t) \quad (9)$$

where $\omega_{IF} = 29.75$ MHz is the IF frequency at the output of the Element Separator (ES). G_k , δ_k , ψ_k stand for the gain, time delay and phase shift introduced in the k-th element channel. Although these values are dependent on element channels, they have the same effects on different MA user signal going through the same element channel. Fixed values of G_k , δ_k , and ψ_k are used here to simplify the modelling and analysis. $n'_k(t)$ is a bandpass noise process derived from $n''_k(t)$ going through FDM, downlink propagation and de-FDM. To simplify the analysis, $n'_k(t)$ is assumed to be a baseband Gaussian process centered at 29.75MHz and expressed

as

$$n'_k(t) = n_{k,c}(t) \cos(\omega_{IF} t + \Psi_k) - n_{k,s}(t) \sin(\omega_{IF} t + \Psi_k) \quad (10)$$

where $n_{k,c}(t)$ and $n_{k,s}(t)$ are independent baseband Gaussian process with same power as $n'_k(t)$ and Ψ_k is an arbitrary phase angle.

Conceptually, if the phase shift and element channel gain in Equation (9) are known, the problem of pointing the antenna array at a given user direction can be achieved by summing the user signal with the phase and amplitude adjusted for each element channel. Although $\delta_{U,k}$ is in the range of 2 nsec as mentioned previously, δ_k can be as large as 120 nsec. For 3.06 Mcps chip rate, the PN chip duration is about 320 nsec. Direct summation of the received element channel signals, $E'_k(t)$, $k=1,\dots,30$, even with phase and gain compensated will reduce the signal power dramatically since the baseband PN spread QPSK (PN_QPSK) signal are not aligned among element channels.

The all-digital implementation of the MAR beamforming equipment after ES takes the advantages provided by a digital system. The major advantage in this case is that after the digitization process, data can be passed to all of the 12 AGIPA's where it can be handled exactly the same way. The processes of digitization, delay adjustment and the extraction of real and imaginary parts of a QPSK signal is accomplished in the Analog to Digital converter, Variable Tap Delay Line, and Quadrature Splitter (AD_VTDL_QS). Illustrated in Figure 3 shows the functional block diagram of AD_VTDL_QS and the design of 32 tap FIR filter. The element channel signal, $E'_k(t)$, is sampled at a rate of 17 Msps and quantized into an eight bits digital. This quantized signal then goes through variable tap delay line for delay adjustment at a resolution of 58.82 nsec as the VTDL is clocked at 17 MHz. The real and imaginary part of PN_QPSK signal is extracted by multiplying with sine and cosine of 4.25 MHz. A bank of 32 tap FIR filters are used after quadrature splitting to remove the possible DC bias created in the analog to digital conversion and to provide the fine delay adjustment. By selecting appropriate 32 tap FIR filter one can accomplish a fine delay adjustment with a resolution of 7.35 nsec. [2]

To remove the discrepancy on δ_k , the delay equalization process can be described as follows. At the beginning of the service, beamformer will pass the element channel signal one by one to the Integrated Receiver (IR). The IR correlates the incoming element channel signals with the beacon PN to estimate the value of $\delta_{0,k} + \delta_k$. This estimation is feedback to AD_VTDL_QS to equalize the delay, $\delta_{U,k} + \delta_k$. For the element channel with small value of $\delta_{U,k} + \delta_k$, the signal is delayed more by the combination of coarse delay in VTDL and fine delay in QS. Denote the delay adjustment for k-th element channel as τ_k . After the equalization cycle, the phasor, $\phi_U(t-\delta_{U,k}-\delta_k)$ which carries PN and QPSK information will be equalized into $\phi_U(t-\delta_{U,k}-\delta_k-\tau_k) = \phi_U(t-\Delta\tau_{U,k}-T)$, where T stands for the overall delay after AD_VTDL_QS and is assumed to be the same among the element channels. $\Delta\tau_{U,k}$ is the residual in time delay after the equalization process. This value depends on the accuracy in the estimation of the element channel delay by IR and the resolution in the delay adjustment in AD_VTDL_QS. Usually, the latter has greater effect on $\Delta\tau_{U,k}$ than the former if the correlation time in IR can be increased to accurately estimate the delay. We can then model $\Delta\tau_{U,k}$ as a random variable uniformly distributed in $[-3.675, 3.675]$ nsec, since the resolution of the fine delay is 7.35 nsec.

Combining the effects of digitizing, delay equalization, and quadrature splitting, the output of the AD_VTDL_QS can be shown [2] to be

$$\begin{aligned}
X_{k,R}(m) &= \sum_{u=0}^{10} \sqrt{G_k} \cdot A_u \cos \left[\varphi_u \left(\frac{m}{f_s} - \Delta\tau_{u,k} - T \right) + \theta_u + \phi_{u,k} + \psi_k + \psi'_k \right] \\
&+ \sqrt{G_k} \left[n_{k,c} \left(\frac{m}{f_s} \right) \cos (\Psi_k + \psi'_k) - n_{k,s} \left(\frac{m}{f_s} \right) \sin (\Psi_k + \psi'_k) \right] \\
X_{k,I}(m) &= \sum_{u=0}^{10} \sqrt{G_k} \cdot A_u \sin \left[\varphi_u \left(\frac{m}{f_s} - \Delta\tau_{u,k} - T \right) + \theta_u + \phi_{u,k} + \psi_k + \psi'_k \right] \\
&+ \sqrt{G_k} \left[n_{k,c} \left(\frac{m}{f_s} \right) \sin (\Psi_k + \psi'_k) + n_{k,s} \left(\frac{m}{f_s} \right) \cos (\Psi_k + \psi'_k) \right] \quad (11)
\end{aligned}$$

where ψ'_k is the additional phase shift due to delay equalization in k -th element channel. This value depends on element channel and can be absorbed into ψ_k . Similarly, the overall delay, T , is the same for all element channels and therefore can be neglected. $f_s=8.5$ Msps is the rate that the real and imaginary parts of PN_QPSK signal is sampled. In next section, the beamforming and calibration processes are operated based on $X_{k,R}(m)$ and $X_{k,I}(m)$. The complex expression on the baseband equivalent PN_QPSK signal will provide theoretic insight into these processes. Let's express the output of AD_VTDL_QS as $x_k(m) = x_{k,R}(m) + j x_{k,I}(m)$ and choose $\Psi_k = -\psi'_k$ (since Ψ_k is arbitrary), Eq.(11) can be rewritten as

$$X_k(m) = \sum_{u=0}^{10} S_{u,k}(t) + n_k(t) \Big|_{t=\frac{m}{f_s}} = X_k(t) \Big|_{t=\frac{m}{f_s}} \quad (12)$$

i.e., the sampled output of AD_VTDL_QS includes the sampled baseband equivalent PN_QPSK signal for all the MA users and the sampled baseband Gaussian noise process. The baseband equivalent PN_QPSK signal for user u at k -th element channel is given by

$$S_{u,k}(t) = \sqrt{G_k} \cdot A_u \exp \{ j [\varphi_u (t - \Delta\tau_{u,k}) + \theta_u + \phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \} \quad (13)$$

Compared with Equation (1), $S_{u,k}(t)$ is the baseband equivalent PN_QPSK signal with time delay $\Delta\tau_{u,k}$, and phase shift $\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k$. The complex baseband noise for k -th element channel, $n_k(t)$, is given by

$$n_k(t) = \sqrt{G_k} \cdot [n_{k,c}(t) + j n_{k,s}(t)] \quad (14)$$

3. Beamforming Processes

Although the operation of the beamforming is implemented in digital domain, the beamforming process is presented in the following based on $X_k(t)$, $S_{u,k}(t)$ and $n_k(t)$ in Eqs. (12), (13) and (14) to gain some insights. Basically, the beamforming process is accomplished by combining the weighted thirty element channel signals as illustrated in Figure 3. Each of the element signal, $X_k(t)$, is adjusted by the amplitude adjustment and phase shift, w_k , before being summed to produce the output $f(t)$. The problem is then to find the optimal weighting, W_{opt} . The choice of the optimal weight is determined using certain optimization criteria and is dependent on the mode of operation in the beamformer. There are three operation modes implemented in the beamforming equipment.

Before further discussion on the beamforming process, let's look at the characteristic of the signal at the input of the combiner. Rewrite $S_{u,k}(t)$ in Eq. (13) as

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{u,k}(t) &= \sqrt{G_k} \cdot A_u \exp \{ j [\varphi_u (t - \Delta\tau_{u,k}) + \theta_u + \phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \} \\
&= [A_u \exp \{ j [\varphi_u (t - \Delta\tau_{u,k}) + \theta_u] \}] \cdot [\sqrt{G_k} \exp \{ j [\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \}] \quad (15)
\end{aligned}$$

For a specific user, the second part of $S_{u,k}$ contains the phase shift

and the amplitude variation among element channels. The first part is basically the same among element channels except the differences in $\Delta\tau_{u,k}$. Its effect on the signal after beamforming will be insignificant since it is very small compared to PN chip time. Therefore, the first part can be assumed to be the same for all element channels and considered as a common factor of the user signal among different element channels. Denote the common factor by $c_u(t)$ and the second part by $d_{u,k}$. Then $S_{u,k}(t)$ can be approximated by

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{u,k}(t) &= [A_u \exp \{ j [\varphi_u (t - \Delta\tau_u) + \theta_u] \}] \cdot [\sqrt{G_k} \exp \{ j [\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \}] \\
&= c_u(t) \cdot d_{u,k} \quad (16)
\end{aligned}$$

From the point of view of a beamformer, $c_u(t)$ contains the desired user baseband signal information and $d_{u,k}$ contains the discrepancy among element channels. The operation of beamforming should preserve $c_u(t)$ while compensating for the discrepancy among $d_{u,k}$'s.

For k -th element channel, the signal power is given by $G_k E \{ |c_u(t)|^2 \}$ and the noise power is $G_k P_{n,k}$, where $P_{n,k}$ is defined as

$$P_{n,k} = E \{ |n_{k,c}(t) + j n_{k,s}(t)|^2 \} = 2 \cdot \sigma_k^2 \quad (17)$$

where σ_k is the standard deviation of $n_{k,c}$ and $n_{k,s}$ since they are independent Gaussian process with the same power. The k -th element channel signal to noise ratio to the input of the combiner is

$$SNR_{in}(k) = \frac{G_k E \{ |c_u(t)|^2 \}}{G_k P_{n,k}} = \frac{A_u^2}{2\sigma_k^2} \quad (18)$$

(1) Pointing mode

In this mode, a beamformer points the antenna array toward a given MA user. Conceptually, if $SNR_{in}(k)$ are the same among element channels, the maximum signal voltage is achieved when w_k is chosen to be

$$w_k = (\sqrt{G_k})^{-1} \exp \{ -j [\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \} \quad (19)$$

since by using this w_k , the phase discrepancy among element channels will be compensated by multiplying $\exp \{ -j [\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \}$. For each signal channel, multiplying a constant doesn't change the SNR

ratio. The amplitude factor $(\sqrt{G_k})^{-1}$ is then utilized to compensate for the signal amplitude discrepancy among element channels. When $SNR_{in}(k)$ are different, the weight is modified to be proportional to the input SNR, i.e.,

$$\begin{aligned}
w_k &= (\sqrt{G_k})^{-1} \exp \{ -j [\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \} \cdot SNR_{in}(k) \\
&= A_u^2 \cdot (\sqrt{G_k}) \exp \{ -j [\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k] \} / (G_k P_{n,k}) = v \cdot d_{u,k}^* / (G_k P_{n,k}) \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

since A_u^2 is the same for all 30 element channels and can be assigned by a constant, v . The SNR at the output of the combiner is discussed in the adaptive mode.

(2) Adaptive Mode

In this mode the optimal weight is derived to maximize the signal to noise ratio at the output of the combiner. Consider the signal plus noise vector

$$X = [X_1(t), X_2(t), \dots, X_{30}(t)]^T = X_s + X_n \quad (21)$$

where the X_s and X_n are the signal and noise vector at the input of the beamformer. There might exist more than one MA user, however, one beamformer is dedicated for each MA user and the signal power of an MA user is usually much less than the noise power. Thus, for

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the interest of one beamformer, we can treat $S_{u,k}(t)$ as the only MA user signal. The output of the combiner can be split in the same way,

$$f(t) = W^T X = W^T X_s + W^T X_n = f_s(t) + f_n(t) \quad (22)$$

From Eq. (16) X_s can be written as

$$X_s = c_u(t) \cdot [d_{u,1}, \dots, d_{u,30}]^T = c_u(t) \cdot D_u \quad (23)$$

where D_u is the vector containing the phase shift and the amplitude variation among element channels. The output signal power may be written as

$$P_s = E\{|f_s(t)|^2\} = E\{c_u(t)^2\} \cdot [W^T D_u]^T \quad (24)$$

Similarly, the output noise power is

$$P_n = W^T M_n W \quad (25)$$

where W^T is the Hermitian of W , and M_n is the noise correlation matrix defined by

$$M_n = E\{X_n \cdot X_n^T\} \quad (26)$$

The quantity to be maximized in the Adaptive mode is

$$SNR = P_s / P_n = E\{|c_u(t)|^2\} \cdot [W^T D_u]^T / W^T M_n W \quad (27)$$

Based on the fact that M_n is Hermitian and positive definite, Applebaum [3,4] showed that the optimal weight vector maximizing the SNR in Eq.(27) is given by

$$W_{opt} = \mu M_n^{-1} D_u \quad (28)$$

where μ is an arbitrary scalar constant. Using the optimal weight vector, the maximum output SNR is

$$SNR_{OUT} = E\{|c_u(t)|^2\} \cdot D_u^T (M_n^{-1})^T D_u \quad (29)$$

The dependence on M_n makes it difficult to analyze the output SNR. A special case is that the noise at the input to the combiner are uncorrelated among element channels, i.e., $E\{n_i(t)n_j(t)\} = 0$ for $i \neq j$. Then the noise correlation matrix is a diagonal matrix and the weight vector can be written as

$$w_k = \mu d_{u,k} \cdot [G_k P_{n,k}]^{-1} = \mu \sqrt{G_k} \exp\{-j[\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k]\} / [G_k P_{n,k}] \quad (30)$$

Compared with Eq.(20), this weight is the same as the one given in pointing mode. The output SNR in this case is given as

$$SNR = \sum_{k=1}^{30} E\{|c_u(t)|^2\} / P_{n,k} = \sum_{k=1}^{30} SNR_m(k) \quad (31)$$

In the ideal case that all the element channel has the same input SNR, the output SNR is 30 times as large as the input SNR and we have a combiner gain of 14.77 dB.

(3) Interference Nulling

When the interference is continuously present in the MA return service, the adaptive algorithm can be applied to null the interference. The optimal weight vector can be derived similarly. First, the input vector to the combiner in Eq. (21) consists of an additional interference vector

$$X = X_s + X_n + X_i \quad (32)$$

where X_i is the interference vector. The quantity to be maximized is then the ratio of signal to noise plus interference. The output noise plus interference power is given by

$$P_{n+i} = W^T M_{n+i} W \quad (33)$$

where the correlation matrix for noise plus interference, M_{n+i} , is defined as

$$M_{n+i} = E\{(X_n + X_i)(X_n + X_i)^T\} \quad (34)$$

Similar to Eq. (27) the signal to noise plus interference ratio is given

by

$$SINR = P_s / P_{n+i} = E\{|c_u(t)|^2\} \cdot [W^T D_u]^T / W^T M_{n+i} W \quad (35)$$

The optimal weight and the corresponding optimal output signal to noise plus interference ratio are found to be

$$W_{opt} = \mu M_{n+i}^{-1} D_u \quad (36)$$

$$SINR_{opt} = E\{|c_u(t)|^2\} \cdot D_u^T (M_{n+i}^{-1})^T D_u \quad (37)$$

Since the adaptive algorithm is utilized to null to interference, this beamforming process is termed adaptive nulling. In the MA return service, the noise is usually much stronger than a MA signal, the correlation measured based on the input to the combiner can be assumed to be M_{n+i} . If the interference is stronger than the noise, M_{n+i} is dominated by the interference. Otherwise, noise will dominate M_{n+i} . In either case, there is no way to separate M_n from M_i . The adaptive algorithm is actually applied to increase the ratio of the desired signal over the undesired corruption.

For some scenario, the interference is not continuously present in the channel. The interference correlation can not be correctly measured. One example is the Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) which is usually modelled as high power, low-duty cycle pulses with specified pulse rate. With the knowledge on the interference characteristic and its direction, the interference correlation matrix can be calculated instead of measured. Similar to Eq. (16), the interference signal in k -th element channel at the input of combiner can be modelled as

$$S_{i,k}(t) = c_i(t) \cdot d_{i,k} = c_i(t) \cdot [\sqrt{G_k} \exp\{j(\phi_{i,k} + \psi_k)\}] \quad (38)$$

where $c_i(t)$ stands for baseband characteristic of the interference. The correlation matrix for the interfere is calculated as

$$M_i = E\{X_i \cdot X_i^T\} \quad (39)$$

where the interference signal vector is given by

$$X_i = [S_{i,1}, S_{i,2}, \dots, S_{i,30}]^T \quad (40)$$

To apply the adaptive algorithm, the correlation matrix is the summation of the measured correlation matrix and the calculated interference correlation matrix. The beamforming process utilizing the measured and calculated correlation matrix is called combination nulling.

4. Calibration Process

To implement the pointing mode beamforming, one requires the information on $d_{u,k}$ and the noise power for the k -th channel. On the other hand, one need $d_{u,k}$ and the correlation matrix of the inputs to the combiner in the adaptive mode beamforming. For the interference nulling, one need additional information on $d_{i,k}$. The noise power and correlation matrix can be obtained by measuring the auto correlation as well as the cross correlation of the inputs of the combiner. Since $\phi_{u,k}$ and $\phi_{i,k}$ can be calculated by knowing user and interference look angles. Therefore, $d_{u,k}$ and $d_{i,k}$ can be found if G_k and ψ_k are available. In STGT, an AGIPA is dedicated to measure $\sqrt{G_k} \exp\{j\psi_k\}$, defined as calibration vector, and provide to other AGIPAs. To see how it works, lets rewrite $d_{u,k}$ as

$$d_{u,k} = \sqrt{G_k} \exp\{j(\phi_{u,k} + \psi_k)\} = \sqrt{G_k} \exp\{j\psi_k\} \cdot \exp\{j\phi_{u,k}\} = v_k \cdot \exp\{j\phi_{u,k}\} \quad (41)$$

where v_k is the k -th component of the calibration vector, $V = [v_1, \dots, v_{30}]$. v_k can be expressed in terms of $d_{0,k}$ as

$$v_k = \sqrt{G_k} \exp\{j\psi_k\} = d_{0,k} \cdot \exp\{-j(\phi_{0,k})\} \quad (42)$$

Thus, the calibration process is accomplished if $d_{0,k}$'s are obtained. In the following we describe the procedure to find $d_{0,k}$. First, from Eq. (12) the sampled beacon signal plus noise at the output of AD_VTDL_QS is given by

$$S_{0,k}(m) + n_k(m) \approx \left[A_0 \exp \left\{ j \left[\varphi_0 \left(\frac{m}{f_s} - \Delta\tau_0 \right) + \theta_0 \right] \right\} \right] \cdot d_{0,k} + n_k(m) \quad (43)$$

Compared with Eq. (2), $c_0(m/f_s) = A_0 \exp \{ j [\varphi_0(m/f_s - \Delta\tau_0) + \theta_0] \}$, stands for the beacon PN with some delay and phase shift. By multiplying $\exp \{-j [\varphi_0(m/f_s - \Delta\tau_0) + \theta_0]\}$ to $S_{0,k}(m)$, signal samples within element channel will be in phase. Therefore, the multiplied samples can be accumulated to increase signal to noise ratio and provide accurate estimation on $d_{0,k}$. In the MA return system, the Integrated Receiver dedicated for calibration process generates the recovered beacon PN sequence as

$$RBP(m) = \exp \{ -j [\varphi_0(m/f_s - \Delta\tau_0) + \theta_0] \} \quad (44)$$

This recovered beacon PN sequence is then feedback to correlate $S_{0,k}(m) + n_k(m)$ for N samples. The output of the correlator, divided by NA_0 , is found to be

$$\begin{aligned} R_k(N)/NA_0 &= \left[\sum_{m=1}^N [S_{0,k}(m) + n_k(m)] \cdot RBP(m) \right] / NA_0 \\ &= d_{0,k} + \left[\sum_{m=1}^N n_k(m) \cdot RBP(m) \right] / NA_0 \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

If the signal to noise ratio of $R_k(N)/NA_0$ is sufficiently large, $d_{0,k}$ can be accurately estimated by $R_k(N)/NA_0$. The noise part of $R_k(N)/NA_0$ is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} & \left[\sum_{m=1}^N n_k(m) \cdot RBP(m) \right] / NA_0 \\ &= \sqrt{G_k} / NA_0 \cdot \sum_{m=1}^N \exp \{-j [\varphi_0(m/f_s - \Delta\tau_0) + \theta_0]\} \cdot [n_{k,c}(m/f_s) + j n_{k,s}(m/f_s)] \\ &= \sqrt{G_k} / NA_0 \cdot \sum_{m=1}^N \{ n'_{k,c}(m/f_s) + j n'_{k,s}(m/f_s) \} \\ &= \sqrt{G_k / NA_0} \cdot \{ Rn_{k,c}(N) + j Rn_{k,s}(N) \} \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where $n'_{k,c}$ and $n'_{k,s}$ are the real and imaginary of the multiplication of the recovered PN and the k -th element channel noise. It is reasonable to assume that the beacon PN is independent of the noise. Therefore $n'_{k,c}$ and $n'_{k,s}$ are independent each other and have the same power of σ_k^2 . $Rn_{k,c}(N)$ and $Rn_{k,s}(N)$ stand for the results after summing N samples of $n'_{k,c}$ and $n'_{k,s}$ respectively. Both of them are modelled as Gaussian random variables with variance $\sigma_k^2(N) = E \{ Rn_{k,c}(N) \} = E \{ Rn_{k,s}(N) \}$ (47)

The output noise power after correlating N samples is $2G_k\sigma_k^2(N)/NA_0^2$. The output signal power is G_k . Denote the output signal to noise ratio as ρ_k^2 , then

$$\rho_k^2 = N^2 \cdot A_0^2 / 2 \cdot \sigma_k^2(N) \quad (48)$$

If both $n'_{k,c}(m/f_s)$ and $n'_{k,s}(m/f_s)$ in Eq.(46) are independent, identically, distributed samples with variance σ_k^2 , then $\sigma_k^2(N)$ in Eq.(47) is equal to $N \sigma_k^2$. The output SNR is then given by

$$\rho_k^2 = N \cdot A_0^2 / 2 \sigma_k^2 = N \cdot \text{SNR}_{in}(k) \quad (49)$$

i.e., the SNR increases N times after correlating N samples. If $n'_{k,c}(t)$ and $n'_{k,s}(t)$ have a brick-wall shaped noise power spectrum density with one sided bandwidth B_w , It was shown in [5] that if the sampling rate, f_s , is larger than $2 B_w$ the output SNR is given by

$$\rho_k^2 = N_{eq} \cdot \text{SNR}_{in}(k) \quad (50)$$

where N_{eq} is the equivalent number of independent noise samples. N_{eq} is related to N by

$$N_{eq} = N \cdot 2B_w / f_s \quad (51)$$

5. Summary

For TDRSS S band MA return signals, a phase-array antenna with 30 elements at TDRS has its beamforming performed on the ground at STGT. There are a total of twelve AGIPA's at STGT for the calibration and the beamforming processes. Ten of the AGIPA's are available to serve MA return users, one is used for calibration, and one is a hot spare [1]. Any of the twelve AGIPA's are able to perform either beamforming or calibration process when it is commanded to do so. The analysis of various operational modes including beamforming, nulling, and calibration processes are presented in this paper.

References

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44.3.5

Figure 1: MABE Return System

Figure 2: Geometry of Array Antenna Path Delay

Figure 3a: Design of 32 tap FIR Filter

Figure 3b: Analog to Digital Converter, Variable Tape Delay Line and Quadrature Splitter

44.3.7

Figure 4: AGIPA Weight Generator and Combiner

44.3.7